

Pword-report

Language name: **Mon (LID 2047).**
 Name: René Schiering (University of Leipzig).
 Sources: Bauer, Christian 1982. *Morphology and Syntax of Spoken Mon*.
 (Ph.D.-Dissertation, University of London). London: SOAS.
 DiCanio, Christian 2005. "Expressive Alliteration in Mon and Khmer."
UC Berkeley Phonology Lab Annual Report 2005: 337-393.
 Guillon, Emmanuel 2003. *Parlons Mon. Langue et civilisation*. Paris:
 L'Harmattan.
 Jenny, Mathias 2005. *The Verb System of Mon*. (ASAS, 19). Zürich:
 Universität Zürich.
 Internet version of The Ethnologue, Vol. 15 (2005).
www.ethnologue.com, 04/27/2006.
 Date completed: 05/03/2006.

I Language Profile

of speakers: 850,530 (742,900 in Myanmar, 107,630 in Thailand).
 Spoken in: Burma (Myanmar), Thailand.
 Contact languages: Burmese, Thai.
 Status: Not an official language in Burma or Thailand. However, literature,
 music and newspapers are written in Mon.
 Prospects: Bilingualism in Mon and Burmese/Thai. Younger speakers are often
 monolingual in Burmese or Thai, which hints at endangerment.
 Structural results: Phonological, lexical and structural influences of varying degrees from
 Burmese and Thai, respectively. Loans exhibit some phonological
 peculiarities with respect to stress placement, phonotactics and word
 length (mentioned below in passing).

II Morpheme Types

1. Stem

2. Restricted pre-posed formative

p-, *pə-*, *hə-* 'causative'

- | | | |
|-----|------------------------------|---|
| (1) | a. <i>làc</i> 'break down' | b. <i>p-lac</i> 'break down sth.' |
| | c. <i>pə-lac</i> 'tear down' | d. <i>hə-làc</i> 'blast away' (Jenny 2005: 121) |

3. Restricted infixal formative

-ə- 'causative'

- | | | |
|-----|-----------------------------|---|
| (2) | a. <i>klɔʔ</i> 'cross over' | b. <i>k-ə-lɔʔ</i> 'take across' (Jenny 2005: 121) |
|-----|-----------------------------|---|

4. Semi-restricted pre-posed formative (auxiliary verb)

paʔ periphrastic causative marker

- | | | |
|-----|-----------------------------|--|
| (3) | a. <i>làc</i> 'break down' | b. <i>paʔ(kɔ) làc</i> 'make break down' |
| | c. <i>klɔʔ</i> 'cross over' | d. <i>paʔkɔ klɔʔ</i> 'make cross over' (Jenny 2005: 121) |

Notice: © 2006 Autotyp. All data from these reports must include citations for both the
 primary reference source(s) and the authors of the reports.

5. Unrestricted post-posed formatives

raʔ ‘focus/assertive’, *noŋ* ‘focus/assertive’, for details see Jenny (2005: 137ff.)

- (4) mətəkə yətha krip mən̄ŋ ʔətao kəh **raʔ**.
 motorcar train run STAY on.top TOP **FOC**
 ‘Cars and trains run up there.’ (Jenny 2005: 143)

- (5) həʔuy dəh khəh mən̄ŋ **noŋ**.
 medicine 3 good STAY **ART**.
 ‘Their medicine was definitely good.’ (Jenny 2005: 147)

kəh ‘definiteness’, for details see Bauer (1982: 322ff.)

- (6) kwan nəʔ **kəh**
 village this DEF
 ‘this village (def.)’ (Bauer 1982: 105)

III Syllable

Syllable Structure

The attested syllable types in (7) can be captured by the overall canonical syllable structure in (8).

- (7) CV, CVC, CCV, CCVC, cəCV, cəCVC, cəCCV, cəCCVC
 (8) (cə)C(C)V(C)

Although the pre-syllable *cə* is treated as part of the syllable structure by Jenny (2005: 33ff.) and other authors in this research tradition, (8) is more convincingly analyzed as the phonotactic structure of disyllabic native words and derivatives (prefixed or infixes words) by Bauer (1982: 135, 110).

Bauer (1982: 45ff.) lists seven diphthongs which may appear in the V slot of the above syllable shell, namely /ui/, /oi/, /ai/, /oa/, /œ/, /ao/ and /ea/. Arguably, these diphthongs are VC sequences at the phonological level. Vowel length is not phonemic in the language.

Monosyllabic words

All of the above syllable types can be minimal free forms. (9) gives an example of the minimal word. [RS: Open syllables are reported to be long at the word level (Bauer 1982: 99), therefore we would expect the vowel in (8) to be lengthened phonetically. On the basis of such evidence one could posit a bimoraic minimality constraint for Mon words].

- (9) ʔa ‘go’ (Jenny 2005: 33ff.)

Vowel-initial words

According to the syllable structure in (8), the onset consonant is obligatory, i.e. there are no vowel-initial words. However, pre-syllables may lack the onset consonant in disyllabic words, cf. (10).

- (10) a. *əreək* ‘alcoholic drink’ b. *ətao* ‘on, above’ (Bauer 1982: 56)

With respect to word-initial onsets, lexical words and function words seem to behave alike. [Note, however, that some onsets of ‘enclitic’ particles originated from re-syllabification, which suggests that function words were vowel-initial at some point, e.g. the absolute question marker */a/ > /ta/ ~ /na/ (Bauer 1982: 97)].

Polysyllabic words

Native monomorphemic words can maximally be disyllabic, in which case they conform to the syllable structure given in (8) above. In such words, clusters of two consonants are restricted to word-medial position, i.e. word-initial onset clusters and word-final coda clusters are prohibited. [RS: Note that onset clusters are allowed in monosyllabic words]. The first syllable may contain a schwa vowel but no other vowel.

There seems to be no variation across lexical categories.

Monomorphemic trisyllables and tetrasyllables are only attested in loan words and are presumably broken down into several mono- or disyllabic domains for the sake of phonological rules.

Superheavy syllables

No superheavy syllables are reported for Mon. [RS: However, if the V slot in (8) is filled by a diphthong and a coda consonant is present, this would give us a word-final superheavy syllable, cf. *paik* ‘to split’ (Bauer 1982: 45). Given the phonotactic constraints of the language superheavy syllables should be restricted to word-final position].

IV Tone & Stress

Register (“Quasi-Tone”)

There are no distinctive tonal contrasts in Mon. However, in the realization of vowels we find a distinction between light register and heavy register, i.e. different phonation types in the realization of vowels/rhymes which are dependent on the initial consonant, the rhyme consonant or both (Jenny 2005: 36f.). In monosyllabic words, the initial plosives /k, c, t, p/ co-occur with both registers, the voiced continuants /y, w, r, l, ŋ, ɲ, n, m/ control the first register, whereas /ʔ, d, ʙ, s, h/ control the second register. [Compare the diachronic scenario for tonogenesis in South East Asian languages proposed by Haudricourt (1954)].

In disyllabic words, the vowel register of the first vowel is determined by the word-medial consonant (Bauer 1982: 74). Bauer (1982: 8) also describes a rule of Vowel Register Assimilation in which the vowel of the first syllable in a di- or trisyllabic word assimilates to the vowel register of the second/final syllable (11). This rule is restricted to (monomorphemic) Indo-Aryan loans and native derived words which include the prefix /ʔiʔ-/ and a stem (see also DiCanio 2005).

- (11) a. /ʔuʔcàn/ => [ʔùʔcàn] (Bauer 1982: 8)
 b. /ʔuʔpətè/ => [ʔùʔpətè] (̀ marks heavy register)

Stress

Bauer (1982: 99ff.) distinguishes four degrees of stress: zero (unstressed), primary stress, secondary stress and tertiary stress. His analysis of stress placement distinguishes four domains: polysyllables in isolation, compound, phrases, and the sentence, where compounds and phrases are subsumed under one heading. (For a discussion of compound and phrasal stress, see sections VIII and X). The following examples, taken from Bauer (1982: 99ff.), illustrate the various attested stress patterns with words of varying degrees of morphological complexity and phonological length.

- (12) a. /'tɛm/ 'to know' (stem, monosyllabic)
 b. /pə'tɛm/ 'to inform' (prefix+stem, disyllabic)
 c. /,ə'khɛ/ 'during' (prefix+stem, disyllabic)
 d. /ɲiʔ'ɲɛʔ/ 'a little (bit)' (stem+stem, disyllabic)
 e. /,cɔŋhə'kùì/ 'to cause to burn' (stem+stem, trisyllabic)
 f. /hə,ʔom'cih/ 'to fall down' (stem+stem, trisyllabic)

- Primary stress is placed on the final syllable of polysyllabic words.
- Secondary stress appears on the initial syllable of disyllabic and trisyllabic words.
- Tertiary stress is realized on the medial syllable of trisyllabic words.
- The initial syllable of native disyllabic words and trisyllables remains unstressed; in some cases, trisyllables have secondary stress on the initial syllable and unstressed medial syllables. (Note that tri- and tetrasyllables are loans).

Summarizing these stress rules, the phonological word may be defined as a sequence of a syllable with zero or secondary stress plus a syllable with primary stress (Bauer 1982: 116). In one (controversial) case, stress placement seems to make a lexical contrast. [RS: However, there is a confound in the extrametrical status of *kòh*, see VI].

- (13) /ɲèh'kòh/ 'who?' vs. /'ɲèh,kòh/ 'they, them, any' (Bauer 1982: 96)

Register may occur irrespective of the presence or degree of stress in a syllable, i.e. vowel register and stress are independent of each other (Bauer 1982: 96).

V Other Non-concatenative Processes

With a few verbs causative formation makes use of suppletion. Accordingly, the causative of *klɔŋ* 'come' is realized by the suppletive stem *nɛŋ* (Jenny 2005: 130). In processes of word formation like nasalization and labialization the initial consonant of monosyllabic words gets replaced: *nɛk* 'stake' *tɛk* 'to strike' (Bauer 1982: 117, 144).

VI "Free" Grammatical Morphemes

Less cohering prefixes

With respect to prefix+stem combinations, the prefix /ʔiʔ-/ exhibits deviant properties when compared to other prefixes in the language. Unlike other prefixes, which can only contain a schwa vowel, it contains a full vowel. This affix participates in Register Assimilation as discussed under IV and sometimes receives the same degree of stress as the stem does (Bauer 1982: 100).

Clitics

As for clitics, stress placement in noun phrases reveals the special status of these elements. If the definiteness marker /kòh/ closes a noun phrase, the preceding noun receives primary stress counter to the more general phrase-final stress pattern. [RS: This suggests that the element prosodically attaches at the level of the phonological phrase].

- (14) a. /,kwan 'mòà/ 'a village'
 b. /'kwan ,kòh/ 'the village'
 c. /,kwan 'nɔʔ ,kòh/ 'this village (def.)' (Bauer 1982: 105)

However, if /kòh/ i) is part of a disyllabic word such as /ʔiʔkòh/ ‘that’, ii) gets reduplicated or iii) plays an anaphoric role in expanded noun phrases, it shows regular final stress. Clitic-like particles may also be contracted with the following stem, in which case they act as proclitics.

(15) /miʔ kɒ mèʔ/ => [miʔ kəmèʔ] ‘mother and father, parents’ (Bauer 1982: 39)

In this respect, they resemble compounds and reduplications which also contract to conform to the canonical syllable structure given in (8).

Phrase-final, clitic-like particles, such as the focus markers exemplified in (4) and (5), do not exhibit any special behavior with respect to phonological constraints or processes. Their phonotactic composition conforms to the possible syllable types listed above. [RS: However, it might turn out that none of them contains pre-syllables]. In prosody, they are regularly integrated into the phrasal stress/intonation domain and receive phrase-final stress. At least in one case, such a particle remains outside the domain for stress assignment. The postverbal aspect operator *məŋ* is unstressed and weakened despite its phrase-final position (Jenny 2005: 160).

VII Polymorphemic Stem Forms

Derivatives which result from prefixation of /cə/ syllables or /ə/-infixation conform to the syllabic structure given in (8). In terms of phonotactic constraints, prefixes may contain no more than one onset consonant and may contain only schwa vowels. In such morphologically complex forms, consonant clusters are only allowed in word-medial position. With respect to register, the schwa vowel is neutral, so disyllabic derivatives are not subject to Register Assimilation. [RS: However, note that Register Assimilation spreads leftwards to affect syllables preceding the schwa vowel in (11b)]. Disyllables which result from affixation show the same stress pattern as other native disyllables, i.e. they have regular word-final stress and the first syllable remains unstressed. (For the noteworthy exception of /ʔiʔ-/ see above).

VIII Compounds, Concatenations, Juxtapositions

Compounding

Compounds in Mon may consist of i) two monosyllables, ii) two disyllables, iii) a monosyllable followed by a disyllable or iv) a disyllable followed by a monosyllable. The respective compound members take the shape of one of the syllable types in (7). The various stress patterns are given in (16), see also (12) for some examples.

- (16) a. ₁CVC 'CVC (compound = two monosyllables)
 b. ₁CVC Cə'CVC (compound = one monosyllable + one disyllable)
 c. Cə₁CVC 'CVC (compound = one disyllable + one monosyllable)
 d. Cə₁CVC Cə'CVC (compound = two disyllables)

[RS: Note that stress placement rules in Mon can be described as applying recursively. Stress in the compound members is assigned according to the rules given in IV. In the compound, the stress of the second member is promoted, parallel to the final stress placement at the word level. Note the resemblance of the stress pattern in (16b.) to that of trisyllabic words described in IV and phrasal stress as discussed in X, suggesting that polysyllabic structures of various morphosyntactic compositions are treated alike in prosody].

Compounds consisting of two monosyllables are subject to contraction, which results in the canonical syllable structure of disyllabic words (8), cf. (17).

(17) /təʔ/ + /nəʔ/ => /təʔnəʔ/ => [tənəʔ] ‘these’ (Bauer 1982: 36)

Periphrasis and Serial Verbs

Periphrastic causative formations (18) and serial verb constructions (19) show no special behavior with respect to any aspect of phonology (phonotactics, register or stress). In stress phonology, they seem to behave like compounds or phrases. Since they cannot be interrupted by an intonation break, both are included in the same intonational phrase.

(18) a. *ləc* ‘break down’ b. *paʔ(kə) ləc* ‘make break down’ (Jenny 2005: 121)

(19) *həmèə tən klɿŋ phəc dəh rəp kəʔ.*
 Burmese move.up COME fear 3s catch GET
 ‘The Burmese came up and we were afraid that they would catch us.’
 (Jenny 2005: 104)

IX Reduplication

Reduplicated monosyllables which function as adverbials are subject to a process of contraction, which yields the syllabic structure of disyllabic words given in (8), cf. (20).

(20) /prəh prəh/ => [pəprəh] ‘quickly’

Such reduplications take regular compound stress as described above. The non-contracted form in (20) has final primary stress and secondary stress on the first syllable. The contracted form, however, has an unstressed initial syllable, i.e. in its contracted form the reduplication shows the phonotactic and prosodic structure of a native disyllabic word (see also DiCiano 2005 for a detailed study of reduplication in Mon and Khmer).

X Phrase/Sentence-level Phenomena

Phrases

At the phrase level, primary stress is placed on the final syllable. In trisyllabic phrases, the initial syllable receives secondary stress and the medial syllable receives tertiary stress, cf. the stress pattern of trisyllabic monomorphemic words discussed in IV. Noun phrases exhibit non-final stress if the final syllable of the phrases consists of a clitic, see (14). One phonological process can be identified at the phrasal level: disyllabic sequences of the form CVC.CVC undergo contraction to the phonotactic word shell CəCVC, cf. (15) above.

Clauses/Sentences

Clauses and sentences are characterized by an iambic intonation contour with heavy stress and high pitch on the final syllable. In the available descriptions, rules of /ʔ/-deletion and /h/-deletion with accompanying compensatory lengthening are reported for phrase-final position. Whereas Bauer (1982: 99) describes these as regular processes, Jenny (2005: 147) (commenting on Bauer’s observations) notes occasional blocking of this process when the phrase-final syllable consists of the particle /raʔ/.

XI Other Special Things to Look for

Geminates

The language does not allow geminates.

Foot

There is no explicit analysis of foot structure in the cited literature. However, the disyllabic phonotactic shell of words may be interpreted as an iambic foot. The pre-syllable is characterized by less segments and the lack of stress, whereas the second syllable exhibits a higher degree of syllable weight and obligatorily receives primary stress. Additional evidence for the prosodic domain of the foot comes from stress patterns above the word domain, in which compounds and phrases consisting of four syllables are realized with alternating secondary and primary stresses (Bauer 1982: 103). [RS: In such an analysis, the prosodic foot and the phonological word would be coextensive].